

Vanadium. Part XIII. Oxo-Vanadium (V) Complexes of Substituted Aromatic Hydroxamic Acids

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Oxo-hydroxo bis hydroxamate complexes of vanadium(V) with a large number of substituted aromatic hydroxamic acids have been described. In many cases, the hydroxo complexes have been found to yield alkoxo complexes during their reaction with alcohols. A correlation has been found between the acid dissociation constants of the ligands and the formation of the alkoxo complexes in the solid crystalline state. Spectral characterisation and conductances in methanol have also been reported.

Earlier in this series some detailed studies on oxovanadium complexes of benzo-hydroxamic acid and eleven other substituted aromatic hydroxamic acids have been published^{1,2}. The complexes synthesized can be grouped under the following three categories:

(1) Oxovanadium (IV) bis hydroxamates (where the hydroxamic acids are, benzo-*p*-nitro, *m*-nitro, *p*-methyl and *p*-methoxy benzo-hydroxamic acids).

These were found to be paramagnetic and possessing rose red or green colour.

(2) Oxo-hydroxo-bis hydroxamate vanadium (V). These were violet to violet black and were found to be diamagnetic.

(3) Oxo-alkoxo-bis hydroxamate vanadium (V). These were dark red to orange red and diamagnetic.

The alkoxo derivatives were obtained by refluxing the parent oxo-hydroxo-bis hydroxamate complexes with alcohols. The violet or violet black complexes, in all cases, went into solution in alcohol providing dark red solutions. However, only in few cases, it was possible to isolate the solid, crystalline form of the alkoxo complexes. In most cases it was observed that removal of the alcohol in vacuum merely brought about a total recovery of the original violet black oxo-hydroxo-bis hydroxamate vanadium (V) complexes.

It was anticipated that the substituent in the aromatic ring might be influencing the formation of the alkoxo complexes. On dissolution of the oxo-hydroxo complexes in alcohol, the first reaction involving the colour change should be at least a linking up of the alcohol unit to the OH of the complex through hydrogen bonding. Next there might occur water elimination resulting in the formation of the alkoxo complexes, which could be isolated in the solid crystalline form. It is not entirely unreasonable to appreciate that during the condition after dissolution of the violet black complex in alcohol and prior to the water elimination, some slight dissociation of the hydroxyl H of

1. Dutta and Lahiry, *This Journal*, 1962, 39, 860.

2. Dutta and Lahiry, *This Journal*, 1963, 40, 53.

of the oxo-hydroxo complex probably takes place. Thus the formation of the alkoxo complexes in general probably takes place as follows: (cf. mechanism of ester formation of carboxylic acids^{3,4}).

*Obtained as a result of slight dissociation of OH hydrogen of the complex molecule. The above mechanism has its origin in the esterification of carboxylic acids^{3,4}. The suggestion of the vanadyl bond participating in the mechanism is tentative.

The purpose of the present study is to throw more light on the formation of these alkoxo complexes. For a better understanding, we will present the results of studies with some more substituted aromatic hydroxamic acids. In order to have a better and more complete appreciation of the matter, the dissociation constants of some of the hydroxamic acids have also been evaluated and are being reported in another independent publication⁵. We will here draw the results of that study for the present situation.

Since the dissociation constants are roughly a measure of the donor ability of the hydroxamic acid ligands, we tried to correlate the ester formation with the acid dissociation constants. In order that the hydrogen bonded alcohol molecule may lead to elimination of a water molecule and thence to an alkoxo complex, the -OH hydrogen must be slightly acidic in nature. This is only possible when there is a strongly electron withdrawing group present as a substituent in the aromatic nucleus. Whereas if electron releasing groups are present, the reverse might happen; the -OH hydrogen receiving more electron density would be less acidic, which in turn will not facilitate the formation of alkoxo compounds.

The experimental results entirely confirm this. The respective acid dissociation constants are included for a closer examination (Table I). The dissociation constants clearly indicate that the introduction of an electron withdrawing group brings about an increase of the acid dissociation constant value, i.e. makes the ligands more acidic and hence less efficient as donors, whereas the electron releasing groups bring about the opposite effect. In this context we find the first group of ligands are also just those ligands, with which a series of alkoxo complexes have been isolated. The O-CH₃ derivative is apparently an exception and an explanation on steric ground has already been offered elsewhere³. Whereas with the second group of ligands all that we find is that there is a red solution formed as a result of dissolution of the -OH complexes in alcohols but the hydrogen bonded alcohol adduct is evidently stable in the presence of a large excess of alcohol. As the alcohol is evaporated off the complex adduct also breaks down and reverts back to the violet black oxo-hydroxo complex.

3. Finar, "Organic Chemistry," Longmans Green (E.L.B.S. edition), P. 176.

4. Brewster and McEwen, "Organic Chemistry", Prentice Hall Inc. Englewood Cliffs, N.J. 3rd. Edition, P. 244.

5. Dutta and Ghosh, *This Journal*, under publication.

TABLE I

Hydroxamic acids	*pK ₁	Oxo-hydroxo complexes	Alkoxo complexes
O-NO ₂ C ₆ H ₄ CONHOH	7.05	[VO (OH) (RH) ₂] (i) Violet (ii) Blue	[VO (OX) (RH) ₂] X=CH ₃ , C ₂ H ₅
O-ClC ₆ H ₄ CONHOH	7.85	[VO (OH) (RH) ₂]	[VO (OX) (RH) ₂] X=CH ₃ , C ₂ H ₅ and n-C ₄ H ₉
O-FC ₆ H ₄ CONHOH	8.00	[VO (OH) (RH) ₂]	[VO (OX) (RH) ₂] X=CH ₃ , C ₂ H ₅ , n-C ₃ H ₇ , n-C ₄ H ₉ and n-C ₅ H ₁₁
P-NO ₂ C ₆ H ₄ CONHOH*	8.35	[VO (OH) (RH) ₂]	[VO (OX) (RH) ₂] X=CH ₃ , C ₂ H ₅
m-NO ₂ C ₆ H ₄ CONHOH*	8.40	[VO (OH) (RH) ₂]	X
P-Cl C ₆ H ₄ CONHOH	8.62	[VO (OH) (RH) ₂]	[VO (OX) (RH) ₂] X=CH ₃ , C ₂ H ₅
O-CH ₃ C ₆ H ₄ CONHOH	8.55	[VO (OH) (RH) ₂]	X
C ₆ H ₅ CONHOH†	8.805	[VO (OH) (R'·H) ₂]	[VO (OX) (RH) ₂] X=CH ₃ , C ₂ H ₅
P-(OCH ₃) C ₆ H ₄ CONHOH	9.00	[VO (OH) (RH) ₂]	X

RH₂= a molecule of substituted benzohydroxamic acids.

R'·H₂= a molecule of benzohydroxamic acid.

*[We have found out two dissociation constants of the hydroxamic acids: (1) the acid dissociation constant of the protonated hydroxamic acid in presence of HCl

We have enlisted pK₁ in the above table as it is a better criteria for the donor properties of the ligands.]

TABLE II

Electronic Absorption spectral data

Complex	Solvent	λ _{max}	Molar extinction at λ _{max}
1. [VO (OH) (O-ClC ₆ H ₄ CONHO) ₂]	Ethanol	420 m μ	1540
2. [VO (OC ₂ H ₅) (O-ClC ₆ H ₄ CONHO) ₂]	"	420	1536
3. [VO (OH) (P-ClC ₆ H ₄ CONHO) ₂]	"	440	1956
4. [VO (OC ₂ H ₅) (P-ClC ₆ H ₄ CONHO) ₂]	"	440	1936
5. [VO (OH) (O-FC ₆ H ₄ CONHO) ₂]	"	440	1940
6. [VO (OC ₂ H ₅) (O-FC ₆ H ₄ CONHO) ₂]	"	430	1960
7. [VO (OH) (O-NO ₂ C ₆ H ₄ CONHO) ₂]	"	470-480	1100
8. [VO (OC ₂ H ₅) (O-NO ₂ C ₆ H ₄ CONHO) ₂]	"	480	1092
9. [VO (OH) (P-I-C ₆ H ₄ CONHO)]	"	430	2040
10. [VO (OH) (O-CH ₃ C ₆ H ₄ CONHO) ₂]	"	440-450	1762
11. [VO (OH) (CH ₃ ·NHC ₆ H ₄ CONHO) ₂]	"	450-460	1300

We have one other point to make. That the esterification occurs at the vanadyl -OH rather than at any of the reagent OH is supported, though indirectly by another study which has just been completed in our laboratory⁴. Molybdenum (VI) forms yellow [MoO₄(RH)₂] which dissolves in alcohol and is recovered unchanged after prolonged refluxing in different alcohols. Their analytical result, m.p., spectral and IR evidence support this. Thus it is not quite easy to esterify the ligands.

The visible absorption spectra of these complexes are also presented (Table II).

4. Dutta and Chatterjee, to be published.

In the cases of those ligands where alkoxo complexes have been isolated we recorded the spectra of (1) the solid alkoxo complexes in ethanol and also of (2) the parent oxo-hydroxo complex in the same alcohol. The two absorption spectra are almost superimposable. Besides, the other oxo-hydroxo complexes where alkoxo complex could not be isolated, have also been dissolved in alcohol (ethanol) and their spectra recorded. These indicate that the alcohol adducts and the solid alkoxo complexes do not show much variation in their spectral characteristics, which is not entirely surprising in view of the bands being likely to be charge transfer type. This is substantiated by a high intensity band in near uv visible region with a high molar extinction coefficient which is indicative of a charge transfer band from the ligands to vanadium (V).

Conductance of both the violet oxo-hydroxo complexes and the alkoxo complexes were measured in G.R. methanol in dilute solution and the data presented. These show the complexes as non-electrolytes (Table III).

TABLE III

Conductance measurement

Complex	Concentration	λ in $\text{Ohm}^{-1} \text{ Cm}^2$ mole $^{-1}$
1. [VO (OH) (o-NO ₂ C ₆ H ₄ CONHO) ₂]	0.001 M	2.96
2. [VO (OCH ₃) (,,-NO ₂ C ₆ H ₄ CONHO) ₂]	"	2.66
3. [VO (OH) (,,-Cl-C ₆ H ₄ CONHO) ₂]	"	2.85
4. [VO (OCH ₃) (,,-Cl-C ₆ H ₄ CONHO) ₂]	"	2.51
5. [VO (OC ₂ H ₅) (,,-Cl-C ₆ H ₄ CONHO) ₂]	"	2.45
6. [VO (OH) (,,-FC ₆ H ₄ CONHO) ₂]	"	2.72
7. [VO (OCH ₃) (,,-FC ₆ H ₄ CONHO) ₂]	"	2.50
8. [VO (OC ₂ H ₅) (,,-FC ₆ H ₄ CONHO) ₂]	"	2.41
9. [VO (OH) (p-ClC ₆ H ₄ CONHO) ₂]	"	2.5
10. [VO (OCH ₃) (p-ClC ₆ H ₄ CONHO) ₂]	"	2.2
11. [VO (OC ₂ H ₅) (p-ClC ₆ H ₄ CONHO) ₂]	"	2.2
12. [VO (OH) (o-CH ₃ C ₆ H ₄ CONHO) ₂]	"	2.36
13. [VO (OH) (p-IC ₆ H ₄ CONHO) ₂]	"	2.21

EXPERIMENTAL

The syntheses of the reagents have been described elsewhere⁵.

Oxo-hydroxo-bis-O-Chlorobenzohydroxamate Vanadium (V). O-Chlorobenzohydroxamic acid (1.5 g) was suspended in warm water (300 ml) and dilute sodium hydroxide solution was added with stirring until a clear solution was obtained. Sodium vanadate (0.3 g) dissolved in hot water (40 ml) was added to the solution of O-Chlorobenzohydroxamic acid. On adjusting the pH to about 2.5-3 by the addition of dilute sulphuric acid (4 N) the deep violet solution deposited dark violet, sparingly soluble crystalline precipitate. The product was filtered, washed thoroughly with cold water and dried over CaCl₂. Found; V, 6.35; N, 11.83%. Req'd. for [VO (OH) (C₆H₄NO₂Cl)₂]: V, 6.58; N, 12.00 percent.

The compound is insoluble in water, benzene, and dichlorobenzene but dissolves in alcohols giving red solution. It is diamagnetic.

FIG. 1 Absorption Spectra 0.0005M in ethanol

FIG. 2 Absorption Spectra 0.0005M in ethanol

A—[VO(OH)(<i>o</i> -FC ₆ H ₄ CONHO) ₂]	A—[VO(OH)(<i>P</i> -ClC ₆ H ₄ CONHO) ₂]	..	..
B—[VO(OC ₂ H ₅)(<i>o</i> -FC ₆ H ₄ CONHO) ₂]	B—[VO(OC ₂ H ₅)(<i>p</i> -ClC ₆ H ₄ CONHO) ₂]	..	..
C—[VO(OH)(<i>o</i> -ClC ₆ H ₄ CONHO) ₂]	C—[VO(OH)(<i>o</i> -CH ₃ C ₆ H ₄ CONHO) ₂]	..	..
D—[VO(OC ₂ H ₅)(<i>o</i> -ClC ₆ H ₄ CONHO) ₂]		..	..

Oxo-methoxy-bis-o-Chlorobenzohydroxamate Vanadium (V). The violet compound prepared as above was dissolved in methanol (20 ml) and the red coloured solution was refluxed on steam bath for 1½ hours, filtered and kept overnight in a refrigerator when it deposited orange red silky crystals. These were filtered and dried over CaCl₂. Found: V, 11.68; N, 6.28 percent. Reqd. for [VO(OCH₃)(C₇H₃NO₂Cl)₂]: V, 11.60; N, 6.38 percent.

Oxo-ethoxy-bis-o-Chlorobenzohydroxamate Vanadium (V). Prepared as above using ethanol (25 ml) instead of methanol and refluxing for 2 hours. Very light and orange-red silky crystals were obtained on keeping in a refrigerator. Found: V, 11.43; N, 6.16 percent. Reqd. for [VO(OC₂H₅)(C₇H₃NO₂Cl)₂]: V, 11.26; N, 6.18 percent.

Oxo-n-butoxy-bis-o-Chlorobenzohydroxamate Vanadium (V). Prepared as above using n-butyl alcohol (20 ml) and refluxing for 4 hours, evaporating to half its volume on water bath and the dark red solution on keeping overnight in refrigerator deposited dark red crystals. Found: V, 10.66; N, 5.87 percent. Reqd. for [VO(OC₄H₉)(C₇H₃NO₂Cl)₂]: V, 10.60; N, 5.82 percent.

Oxo-hydroxy-bis-p-Chlorobenzohydroxamate Vanadium (V). Prepared as for the *o*-Chloro derivative from potassium *P*-Chlorobenzohydroxamate (1 g in 200 ml hot water) and sodium vanadate (0.2 g in 40 ml water) at pH 2.5-3. The violet crystalline precipitate formed was then filtered, washed with hot water, sucked and finally dried over CaCl₂. Found: V, 11.87; N, 6.65 percent. Reqd. for [VO(OH)(C₇H₃NO₂Cl)₂]: V, 12.00; N, 6.88 percent.

Oxo-methoxy-bis-p-Chlorobenzohydroxamate Vanadium (V). Obtained as deep red crystals from the freshly prepared violet compound by refluxing with methanol for 4 hours

following above procedures. Found: V, 11.8; N, 6.18 percent. Req'd. for $[\text{VO}(\text{OCH}_2(\text{C}_7\text{H}_5\text{NO}_2\text{Cl})_2)]$ V, 11.68; N, 6.38 percent.

FIG. 3. Absorption Spectra 0.0005M in ethanol

FIG. 4. Absorption Spectra 0.0005M in ethanol

A— $[\text{VO}(\text{OH})(o\text{-NO}_2\text{C}_6\text{H}_4\text{CONHO})_2]$ „ „ A— $[\text{VO}(\text{OH})(p\text{-IC}_6\text{H}_4\text{CONHO})_2]$ „ „
 B— $[\text{VO}(\text{OC}_2\text{H}_5)(o\text{-NO}_2\text{C}_6\text{H}_4\text{CONHO})_2]$ „ „ B— $[\text{VO}(\text{OH})(\text{CH}_2\text{NH}(\text{C}_6\text{H}_4\text{CONHO})_2)]$ „ „

Oxo-ethoxo-bis-p-chlorobenzohydroxamate Vanadium (V). Prepared as above using ethanol (15 ml) in place of methanol. Obtained as shiny orange red micro crystals. Found: V, 11.48; N, 6.30 percent. Req'd. for $[\text{VO}(\text{OH})(\text{C}_7\text{H}_5\text{NO}_2\text{Cl})_2]$: V, 11.60; N, 6.18 percent.

The original violet compound was taken in n-butanol (15 ml) and on refluxing on water bath produced a deep red solution which was refluxed for 6-7 hours and the residue left on evaporation of the alcohol was the original violet compound. Found: V, 11.81; N, 6.7 percent. Req'd. for $[\text{VO}(\text{OH})(\text{C}_7\text{H}_5\text{NO}_2\text{Cl})_2]$: V, 12.00; N, 6.58 percent.

Oxo-hydroxo-bis-o-nitrobenzohydroxamate Vanadium (V) (violet): o-nitrobenzohydroxamic acid (1 g) was dissolved in hot water (50 ml), cooled and added to a well cooled solution of sodium vanadate (0.2 g in 20 ml water). On adjusting the pH to 3.5-4 by the addition of 4 N H_2SO_4 a violet black crystalline precipitate appeared, rapidly filtered, washed repeatedly with ice cold water, sucked and finally dried over CaCl_2 . Found: V, 11.51; N, 12.40 percent. Req'd. for $[\text{VO}(\text{OH})(\text{C}_7\text{H}_5\text{N}_2\text{O}_4)_2]$: V, 11.39; N, 12.50 percent.

Oxo-hydroxo-bis-o-nitrobenzohydroxamate Vanadium (V) (blue): The above violet compound was precipitated at pH 2-3.5 digested on waterbath for 25-30 minutes and then allowed to stand at room temperature for several hours when the violet colour changed completely to deep blue. This was filtered, washed with hot water and dried over CaCl_2 . Found: V, 11.55; N, 12.38 percent. Req'd. for $[\text{VO}(\text{OH})(\text{C}_7\text{H}_5\text{N}_2\text{O}_4)_2]$: V, 11.39; N, 12.50 percent.

Both the above compounds are somewhat soluble in water when freshly prepared. The colour change from violet to blue is quicker at a lower pH and higher temperature.

Oxo-methoxo-bis-o-nitrobenzohydroxamate Vanadium (V). The violet compound was dissolved in anhydrous methanol (25 ml) and 0.5 g anhydrous sodium sulphate added and the mixture refluxed for 4 hours. The deep-red solution was filtered and kept overnight in refrigerator when beautiful maroon red coloured crystals were deposited. These were

filtered and dried over CaCl_2 . Found: V, 11.26; N, 11.98 percent. Req'd. for $[\text{VO}(\text{OCH}_2)_2(\text{C}_7\text{H}_5\text{N}_2\text{O}_4)_2]_2$: V, 11.04; N, 12.13 percent.

The blue compound also gave the same maroon red methoxo compound by the above treatment.

Oxo-ethoxo-bis-o-nitrobenzo hydroxamato Vanadium (V). Obtained as deep-red crystals as above using ethanol instead of methanol, refluxing for 6 hours, filtering and cooling in refrigerator. Found: V, 10.82; N, 11.62 percent. Req'd. for $[\text{VO}(\text{OC}_2\text{H}_5)_2(\text{C}_7\text{H}_5\text{N}_2\text{O}_4)]_2$: V, 10.71; N, 11.76 percent.

Oxo-hydroxo-bis-o-methylbenzo hydroxamato Vanadium (V). The violet compound was prepared by following the general method at pH 3.5–4. The colour of the dried product is lighter than that of the corresponding compound of *P*-chlorobenzohydroxamic acid. Found: V, 13.23; N, 7.46 percent. Req'd. for $[\text{VO}(\text{OH})(\text{C}_8\text{H}_9\text{NO}_2)_2]_2$: V, 13.21; N, 7.25 percent.

Oxo-hydroxo-bis-p-iodobenzohydroxamato Vanadium (V). Potassium salt of *P*-iodobenzohydroxamic acid (2 g) was suspended in water (500 ml) and concentrated sodium hydroxide solution was added with stirring until it becomes alkaline. It was heated on water bath and filtered. The filtrate was then added to a solution of sodium vanadate (0.4 g in 80 ml water) and the pH of the solution adjusted to 3.5–4 when it deposited a crystalline dark violet precipitate which was filtered, washed repeatedly with hot water and dried over CaCl_2 . Found: V, 8.55; N, 4.70 percent. Req'd. for $[\text{VO}(\text{OH})(\text{C}_7\text{H}_5\text{NO}_2\text{I})_2]_2$: V, 8.38; N, 4.6 percent.

The above compound was dissolved in anhydrous methanol, 0.5 g anhydrous sodium sulphate added, refluxed for 12–14 hours and cooled but deposited no crystals. On evaporation of the methanol the original violet black compound was obtained. Found: V, 8.45; N, 4.8 percent. Req'd. for the violet compound: V, 8.38; N, 4.6 percent.

Oxo-hydroxo-bis-N-methylantranilhydroxamato Vanadium (V). This was prepared following the general method, using *N*-methylantranilhydroxamic acid instead of *O*-chlorobenzohydroxamic acid. The dried product was of a black colour with a greenish tinge. Found: V, 12.16; N, 13.31 percent. Req'd. for $[\text{VO}(\text{OH})(\text{C}_8\text{H}_9\text{N}_2\text{O}_4)_2]_2$: V, 12.26; N, 13.46 percent.

The above black compound was dissolved in methanol (20 ml) refluxed for 10 hours and cooled but deposited no crystals. On evaporation of the methanol the original black compound returned.

Oxo-hydroxo-bis-o-fluorobenzohydroxamato Vanadium (V). This was obtained as dark violet crystalline precipitate following the general method, using *O*-fluorobenzohydroxamic acid in place of *O*-chlorobenzohydroxamic acid. Found: V, 12.83; N, 7.05 percent. Req'd. for $[\text{VO}(\text{OH})(\text{C}_7\text{H}_5\text{NO}_2\text{F})_2]_2$: V, 12.94; N, 7.14 percent.

Oxo-methoxo-bis-o-fluorobenzohydroxamato Vanadium (V). The freshly prepared violet compound was refluxed with methanol for half hour and the clear deep red solution soon deposited dark red silky crystals at room temperature. These were filtered and dried over CaCl_2 . Found: V, 12.49; N, 6.80 percent. Req'd. for $[\text{VO}(\text{OCH}_2)_2(\text{C}_7\text{H}_5\text{NO}_2\text{F})_2]_2$: V, 12.56; N, 6.89 percent.

Oxo-ethoxo-bis-o-fluorobenzohydroxamate Vanadium(V). Obtained as dark red crystals by refluxing the violet compound with ethanol (25 ml) for one hour and cooling in refrigerator. Found: V, 12.00; N, 6.56 percent. Reqd. for $[\text{VO}(\text{OC}_2\text{H}_5)](\text{C}_6\text{H}_3\text{NO}_2\text{F})_2$: V, 12.08; N, 6.63 percent.

Oxo-n-propoxo-bis-o-fluorobenzohydroxamate Vanadium(V). Obtained as deep red crystals by refluxing the violet compound for one hour with n-propanol (15ml) and cooling in refrigerator. Found: V, 11.58; N, 6.54 percent. Reqd. for $[\text{VO}(\text{OC}_3\text{H}_7)](\text{C}_6\text{H}_3\text{NO}_2\text{F})_2$: V, 11.69; N, 6.42 percent.

Oxo-n-butoxo-bis-o-fluorobenzohydroxamate Vanadium(V). Obtained as shining dark-red crystals by refluxing the violet compound for one and a half hour and cooling in refrigerator. Found: V, 11.3; N, 6.05 percent. Reqd. for $[\text{VO}(\text{OC}_4\text{H}_9)](\text{C}_6\text{H}_3\text{NO}_2\text{F})_2$: V, 11.11; N, 6.22 percent.

Oxo-n-amylazo-bis-o-fluorobenzohydroxamate Vanadium(V). The violet compound was refluxed with in n-amyl alcohol (10 ml) for 3 hours and cooled in a refrigerator when beautiful crimson red crystals appeared, filtered and dried over CaCl_2 . Found: V, 11.00; N, 6.01 percent. Reqd. for $[\text{VO}(\text{OC}_5\text{H}_{11})](\text{C}_6\text{H}_3\text{NO}_2\text{F})_2$: V, 11.04; N, 6.06 percent.

General Experimental Methods: Vanadium was estimated as V_2O_5 after carefully igniting the complex under a thick layer of oxalic acid. Nitrogen was estimated by semi micro Dumas technique.

Absorption spectra was recorded in Hilger—Watt $\ddot{\text{U}}$ vispeck spectrophotometer using 1 cm cell and conductance by a Philips conductivity bridge.

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